

A Study of Factors Affecting on Apparel Buying Behaviour

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Abstract:

The world-wide women's clothing market has shown a fast growth pattern. Women have become a significant part of buying clothes. They pay a lot of attention to clothes, thus changing the behaviour of consumers. Forecasting a women's buying habits is a major challenge in meeting these needs. The use of fashion clothes by women has increased considerably.

This article reviews the literature on females' apparel purchasing behaviours. The key intention of the research paper is to categorise altered perspective that can support and monitor future researchers. Researchers reviewed the research literature on women's clothing choices and purchasing behaviour. The overall aim of these studies is to better understand women's clothing preferences and purchasing behaviours. However, the research revealed that rural women prefer to dress more than women in urban areas. The recommendations show that understanding the preferences of women consumers can help clothing companies design quality, well-fitting clothing for women and meet their needs.

Keywords: *behaviour, Clothing Preferences, Purchasing Behaviour, Retail, Women's Clothing*

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1. Introduction

Apparel and ready-to-wear industry ranks high and consumer spending on apparel is also increasing, given these opinions, it is vital to study the fluctuating behaviour of consumers. Clothing is important to everyone as it reflects people culture, personality and interests. People use clothes to improve their personal image, to protect them from hot weather and various weather conditions. People around the world also see clothing as a reflection of current fashion and culture. At the same time, it is an indisputable fact that customers have values that change from customer to customer, such as cooperation, fashion and brand awareness, trust, and emotions.

Indian apparel consumers are experiencing an alteration and are quickly adjusting to fashion trends. Rising disposable earnings, introduction to global trends and apparel brands, and increased stages of trust have led to changes in consumer behaviour. At this intersection, it's fair to say that a successful salesperson should be able to appeal to customers of different ages and classes. This requires improved product packaging and careful product design. Many retailers have begun to analyse the buying behaviour of different types of customers and cut product segmentation, reducing product and promotion based on the characteristics of each customer segment. Product packaging and product presentation are also gaining traction as a way to engage consumers in their in-store shopping experience. This study aims to analyse the clothing purchasing behaviour of retailers. This study shows clothing stores in local stores, international clothing stores and international stores selling different kinds of Indian and Western clothing.

a). Objective:

This article presents a literature review on women's clothing preferences and purchasing. The core agenda of this study is to disclose the clothing preferences of female consumers and their purchasing behaviours. The study also purposes to determine the aspects that affect consumers' decision to buy ready-made clothing from in-store and out-of-town stores.

b). Literature Review:

Researchers investigated the purchasing habits of mature women through observations at department stores and interviews with Finnish women. They identified clothing fashion, fit preference, brand affinity, preferred retailers, and pricing as key factors influencing their buying decisions. Building on these insights, they devised an innovative model to understand mature female consumers' behaviour. [1]

Researchers examined women's purchasing patterns from various perspectives, including customer appearances, reference groups, product specifications, store characteristics, and promotional activities. They noted that women are discerning about brands, with brand image significantly influencing their decision-making process. Effective product branding and loyalty programs can enhance foot traffic for retailers. The purchasing factor is closely tied to the customer's income level. The quality of merchandise emerges as a crucial aspect influencing purchasing behaviour. Additionally, factors such as price, colour, design, style, and comfort are linked to customer buying patterns. Preferences in purchasing aligns with both the age and income of the customer. [2, 3]

Quality stands out as a pivotal feature influencing customers' purchasing decisions. Given the ever-evolving nature of fashion, tailored to the choices and preferences of customers, brand reputation remains a crucial factor in their buying choices. Apparel retailers must carefully heed the demands and requirements of customers to effectively meet their needs and preferences. Various factors influence the purchasing behaviour of working women. Online shopping is particularly favoured by this demographic as it saves time and offers convenience. It allows them to browse products, add items to their shopping carts, and make purchases at their convenience, even during their leisure time. [4, 5]

Impulse buying behaviour exhibits a notable correlation with gender, age, and marital status. Women tend to display more pronounced impulse buying tendencies compared to men. Particularly, unmarried women under the age of 30 are demonstrating a higher propensity for impulse buying. The association of a brand with prestige is strong. Brand awareness exerts a significant influence on customer purchasing behaviour, particularly in the realm of clothing. The perception of a brand profoundly influences consumer buying decisions. Interestingly, men tend to exhibit higher brand consciousness regarding apparel compared to women. Retailers can cultivate a strong brand image in customers' minds through strategic advertising, offering competitive prices, and delivering high-quality products. [6, 7]

Women may alter their brand loyalty based on factors such as brand image, pricing, and the quality of products offered by competing brands. Additionally, the influence of friends plays a significant role in shaping women's purchasing behaviour and can affect brand loyalty. Research on women's compulsive buying behaviour emphasizes the significance of customer attitude in purchasing decisions. Positive moods often lead to increased purchases, whereas negative emotions or dissatisfaction can alter buying behaviour. Retailers capitalize on this by offering enticing deals, prompting customers to buy products they may not necessarily need. Customers typically feel content when they plan their purchases and stick to their intended shopping lists. [8, 9]

The impact of demographic traits, including age, gender, marital status, income, cultural background, occupation, education, and geographic location, on consumer behaviour is well-documented. Consumer behaviour is dynamic and can vary based on the context and situation. Changes in various demographic factors can result in shifts in consumer behaviour patterns. Women tend to be more frequent purchasers of apparel compared to men. Purchase behaviour in this regard is closely linked to consumer behaviour. Women make their buying decisions based on the quality and price of apparel items. They are often willing to travel to find apparel that meet their preferences. [10, 11]

The study delves into the purchasing behaviour of females aged 16 to 45. Middle-aged women within this cluster tend to buy clothing according to the occasion, with a preference for formal wear. The buying decisions of middle-aged females are often influenced by their spouses. Social factors and product characteristics play pivotal roles in shaping women's purchasing behaviour. The study focuses on the apparel buying behaviour of college-going girls. Among young girls, the design of apparel holds paramount importance. Design and style serve as the primary factors guiding apparel selection for this demographic. Additionally, fabric selection plays a crucial role, with priority given to comfortable fabrics in apparel choices. Retailers should ensure their apparel stock aligns with these preferences by prioritizing design, style, and the use of comfortable fabrics. [12, 13]

The shifting consumer behaviour among women can be attributed to trends such as delayed marriage and declining fertility rates. Identifying impulse buying behaviour in women poses significant challenges. This behaviour

presents a major concern for retailers. To address this issue, retailers should focus on strategies such as visual merchandising, offering enticing deals and discounts. Predicting women's purchasing behaviour prior to the point of purchase is highly challenging, as it can change unexpectedly. [14]

The lifestyle of women plays a significant role in shaping their consumer behaviour. Various factors such as demographics, religious beliefs, and cultural norms are intertwined with lifestyle choices, influencing how women make purchasing decisions. Gender plays a pivotal role in influencing buying decisions, with male and female customers exhibiting distinct consumer behaviours even when purchasing the same products. Men typically approach buying decisions analytically and logically, while women tend to make more emotionally driven choices. [15, 16]

A study on the consumer buying behaviour of women's apparel in Malaysia reveals that women prioritize the fit and size of garments, leading them to favour online retailers. Online platforms offer a wide range of size options and varieties, catering to women's preferences. Additionally, women are increasingly opting for online retailers due to time-saving benefits and the availability of discounts on apparel purchases. Women are drawn to online retailing due to factors such as economic growth, increased education levels, and widespread internet access. The plethora of options available for purchasing products online, coupled with post-sales services, makes online shopping appealing to them. The adoption of hassle-free return policies emerges as a crucial element contributing to the triumph of online retailing. Companies should prioritize understanding consumer behaviour to capitalize on these trends and drive profitability. [17, 18]

2. Results and Discussion

Females are influenced by several performance factors while taking a buying decision of apparels that includes price, quality, and assurance. These elements display substantial shares in determining consumer selections in the zone of fashion and clothing.

Women's spending behaviours and decision-making processes are inclined by several elements such as personal values, cultural norms, socioeconomic status, and individual personality traits. Women's profession has an influence on their buying power. Factors such as earnings, employment security, and career development forecasts have an impact on an individual's capability to make purchases and support their family. Additionally, numerous studies have highlighted that working women possess price, quality, and product knowledge.

Price is generally a main concern for many customers. Female assess whether the price of an apparel supports with their perceived worth and affordability. Factors such as personal budget, earnings, and the observed value of the merchandise can influence the price compassion of individual customer. Quality is another fundamental factor that influences apparel purchases. Customers generally seek apparels that are well-made, long-lasting, and can withstand regular wear and washing. The awareness of quality can fluctuate among individuals based on their likings, beliefs, and earlier involvements.

Return policies can also be prevailing elements when it comes to apparel buying. Customers may sense more confident buying apparel items when there is a good return policy in place. Such promises can provide peace of mind and a sense of safety. Also, style, shape, and design are vital concerns for various females when selecting apparels. Women often seek apparels that links with their personal choice, fashion styles, and preferred aesthetics. The style and shape of clothing can add to an individual's self-expression, personality, and overall pleasure with the merchandise. Additionally, cultural inspirations, social customs, and personal beliefs can also impact apparel selection and customer behaviour.

Women's openness to advertising messages is motivated by a different of factors, including personal benefits, traditional background, education, and individual behaviour. Certain types of advertisements, such as those highlighting emotional links or communal connections, may resonate more with females. Many studies have emphasis on understanding the buying behaviour of younger females, there is also value in exploring the buying patterns and preferences of middle-aged and older females. The consumer behaviour of women can change during different life stages, influenced by aspects such as personal development, standard of living, and evolving priorities. Middle-aged and older women often have different requirements, preferences, and buying power, which can considerably influence their buying decisions.

The study of women's consumer behaviour in India, especially the emphasis on metro cities while ignoring the buying patterns in smaller cities. Consumer behaviour can fluctuate substantially between metro cities and smaller

cities due to differences in aspects such as income levels, traditional influences, standard of living, and availability of merchandises and services. It is vital to consider the exclusive features and dynamics of consumer behaviour in smaller cities to develop a comprehensive understanding of women's purchasing patterns. This comprises understanding the influence of local culture, availability of retail infrastructure, and specific merchandise preferences that may differ from metro cities.

Escalating research to smaller cities can help marketers and businesses develop more custom-made policies to encounter the requirements and preferences of women consumers in these areas. It can also contribute to a more common understanding of consumer behaviour in India and assist targeted marketing efforts that resonate with a broader range of customers.

The research gap identified revolves around a study that only emphasizes on the apparel buying behaviour of younger women, excluding the middle-aged and older women. This gap highlights the absence of understanding or knowledge regarding the apparel preferences, motivations, and buying patterns of middle-aged and older women. To fill this research gap, it is important to conduct studies that specially target middle-aged and older women. Such research can discover numerous dimensions, including their style preferences, brand faithfulness, decision-making processes, the influence of societal factors, and the influence of promotion approaches on their purchasing decisions.

By conducting investigation that comprises a varied age range, a more comprehensive understanding of apparel buying behaviour across different generations can be attained. This awareness would prove supportive for marketers, retailers, and fashion designers as they can modify their merchandises, sales promotions, and policies to encounter the certain requirements and likings of middle-aged and older females.

To initiate this research, surveys, interviews, focus groups, or observational studies can be utilized, precisely targeting the desired age groups. Gathering data on demographics, spending habits, motivations, and dominant factors will yield valuable insights into the apparel buying behaviour of middle-aged and older women. The resulting insights can inform promotion plans and decision-making processes in the apparel industry, allowing for improved alignment with the needs and preferences of middle-aged and older women.

Conducting studies precisely targeting women's apparel and accessories is needed for a more detailed understanding of their consumer behaviour. By exploring several features such as buying motivations, product preferences, decision-making processes, fashion styles, community influences, and the impact of advertising strategies, researchers can gain deeper insights into how females make buying decisions in this precise product category. Narrowing the emphasis to women's apparel and accessories permits for a more targeted analysis of their preferences, shopping habits, and the factors that drive their buying decisions. This information is very much valuable for marketers, retailers, and garment manufacturers, as it permits them to mould their merchandises, advertising campaigns, and policies to encounter the definite needs and desires of women in the apparel and accessories segment.

Studying apparel buying behaviour in metro cities of India, neglecting the specific buying patterns and behaviours observed in small cities. This gap proposes that there is a lack of understanding regarding the apparel preferences, motivations, and buying patterns of customers in small cities. To address this research gap, it would be substantial to conduct studies that precisely target small cities in India to gain insights into their unique apparel buying behaviour. This research could discover numerous features, such as fashion preferences, brand varieties, decision-making processes, shopping channels, the impact of local ethos, and the influence of socio-economic issues on their buying decisions.

By conducting research in small cities, a more comprehensive understanding of apparel buying behaviour in different urban contexts can be achieved. This knowledge would be beneficial for marketers, retailers, and garment manufacturers, as it would enable them to modify their merchandises, promotions policies, and distribution channels to justify to the exact requirements and preferences of customers in small towns. Conducting relative studies that analyse the similarities and differences between metro cities and small cities, in terms of apparel buying behaviour, would be advantageous for understanding the deviations in consumer preferences and patterns across different urban areas. The research gap identified concerns to studies that have mostly focused on online apparel buying behaviour, neglecting the apparel buying behaviour within retail outlets. This gap suggests that there is a

lack of awareness regarding the issues that power consumers' apparel buying decisions and behaviours explicitly when shopping in physical retail stores.

To address this research gap, it would be important to conduct studies that precisely target the apparel buying behaviour inside retail outlets. This research could explore various traits, for example the impact of store layout and design, merchandise display and presentation, customer service, pricing policies, and the influence of community relations on consumers' buying decisions within the physical retail atmosphere. By conducting research inside retail outlets, about the features that drive consumers' apparel buying behaviour in offline stores. This information would be favourable for retailers, store managers, and apparel brands as it would permit them to boost their in-store strategies, enhancement the shopping experience, and modify their offerings to encounter the definite requirements and preferences of customers who choose shopping in physical stores.

By addressing this research gap with focused studies on apparel buying behaviour inside retail outlets, researchers can contribute to a more inclusive understanding of consumer behaviour in offline stores. The resulting perceptions can notify retail strategies, store design, customer service practices, and overall decision-making processes, allowing retailers and retail brands to develop the in-store shopping experience and cater to the needs of their customers. Lack of apparel buying behaviour of women studies conducted specifically in India. To address this research gap, it would be appreciated to conduct studies specially focused on apparel buying behaviour within the Indian context. This research could explore several aspects, involving consumer preferences, inspirations, decision-making processes, brand varieties, shopping channels, and the effect of cultural, societal, and commercial factors on apparel buying decisions in India.

By addressing this research gap with focused studies on apparel buying behaviour in India, scholars can contribute to additional comprehensive understanding of consumer behaviour in the Indian apparel market. The resulting insights can update promotion policies, merchandise assortment, and decision-making processes, permitting companies to better fulfil to the requirements and preferences of Indian customers.

3. Conclusion

In this investigation, researchers examined women's preferences and buying habits regarding clothing. They found that women's occupations have a direct impact on their purchasing power as well as that of their families. Furthermore, the study indicates that employed women possess a keen awareness of price, quality, and product specifications, often influenced by others during their shopping endeavours. The study concludes that an individual's clothing purchasing decisions are influenced by various performance factors, including price, quality, and warranty, as well as aspects such as style and fit.

The findings suggest that women generally outperform men in interpreting dress syntax, indicating a higher level of knowledge and sensitivity to clothing cues among women. A study revealed that consumers wearing Indian attire exhibit significant knowledge about clothing. Moreover, these consumers prioritize factors such as quality, variety, and comfort when making purchasing decisions. While research highlights gender disparities in attitudes toward fashion and brands, it also indicates that men share an equal interest in clothing shopping compared to women.

Research has established that women exhibit greater sensitivity to information and content, and are more inclined towards considerations such as education, employment, and marital status while shopping. This response provides insight into the comparative analysis of evolving perceptions and purchasing behaviours between employed and non-employed females in rural India. The findings suggest that the employment status of females significantly impacts their own and their families' purchasing behaviours

4. Scope

The research is based on the age, gender, occupation, income, etc. of female consumers. It includes clothing purchasing behaviours according to variables such as recommendations, influence of sellers and price, quality, advertising, image type, style, etc. The influence of certain factors will impact consumers on their purchase regret. This study helps marketers and stakeholders understand the purchasing behaviour of female consumers and design products based on their needs. It will also be useful for new entrepreneurs who want to enter the women's clothing business. This will enable them to understand the current customers and future prospects of the same segment.

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